

State and Analysis of Ensuring the Effectiveness of the Activities of Construction Materials Production Enterprises of Namangan Region

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Abstract: The article develops the results of an analysis of the state of ensuring the efficiency of enterprises producing building materials in the Namangan region. With the help of research by foreign scientists, mechanisms for increasing the efficiency of production of building materials were analyzed. Investments in the construction sector of Uzbekistan, their analysis and share were studied. As a result of reforms in Uzbekistan in 2017-2022, the construction sector has changed rapidly compared to other sectors of the economy, showing the percentage of people employed in construction and the growth pattern. The influence of external factors on the efficiency of enterprises producing construction materials in the republic is shown.

Keywords: National economy, capital construction, foreign investment, construction industry, industrial products, competitiveness, economic efficiency.

Introduction

The construction sector serves to satisfy the basic necessities of life. As the world's population grows, so do these needs. In countries with economic potential and developed infrastructure, the construction industry is becoming one of the leading sectors of the economy. According to international organizations, "In the near 10-year future (the period until 2030), it is forecasted that the volume of production of construction products will increase by an average of 2.3% annually. In the indicated period, the average annual decrease in the volume of production of construction industry products in developed countries (USA, Japan, EU countries) is observed by 0.1-0.5%, while in developing countries, it is expected to increase by 5.0-8.0%. 1] Development of the building materials industry and ensuring its efficient operation is an urgent task in all countries. It is necessary to achieve this by improving economic and organizational mechanisms and using modern technologies.

Scientific research carried out in different countries allows construction products industry enterprises to make wide use of internal opportunities to increase the efficiency of economic processes in their activities, to form new methods and mechanisms in this regard, to increase the level of competitiveness of construction industry entities and to optimize costs in the field of activity, in accordance with the current needs of the construction quality offered in the construction industry. is focused on improvement, efficiency evaluation mechanisms. Also, by creating additional small systems and databases, a number of scientific studies are being conducted to digitize the construction industry, introduce innovative technologies in the production of building materials and construction of facilities. Currently, priority scientific researches are being carried out in priority directions such as digitalization of the construction

industry, improvement of the system of integrated development of settlements, creation of new construction technologies and optimization of costs in the technological chain of production, increase of the share of construction in the GDP.

To improve the technological and organizational-economic processes in the enterprises of the building materials industry network, which is a component of the construction industry in Uzbekistan, to consistently introduce market mechanisms in the enterprises of the industry and to diversify their production and service processes, to increase the economic potential of the enterprises of the industry through the complete formation of the added value chain in the industry, thereby, great attention is being paid to ensuring employment, meeting the population's needs for construction products, and improving living conditions.

In the Development Strategy of New Uzbekistan for 2022-2026, the priority tasks for the development of the construction products market are defined as "doubling the volume of production of construction materials and widely introducing programs to increase labor productivity in industrial sectors[2]. Ensuring their effective implementation means shortening the duration and cost of housing construction by widely introducing energy-saving materials in the field, and optimizing costs in the production of building materials. In the implementation of these tasks, the organization of housing construction clusters, which include the added value chain from the production of building materials to the design of construction objects and the construction of ready-made multi-storey houses, is of great importance in the regions. On the basis of them, the organizational economic mechanism of enterprises producing construction products will be further improved and integrated relations between individual enterprises will be formed. It is appropriate to further expand scientific research on the development of construction materials production enterprises in these directions.

Literature review

From foreign scientists on the management of the economic efficiency of enterprises producing construction materials: D. Ricardo[3], M.H. Meskon[4], D.J. Rechmen[5], M.H. Meskon[6], K.L. Bowie[7], M. Porter[8], R.Chase[9], E. Demming[10], etc. are covered in scientific works.

At the same time, V.M. Vasil'tsova[11], O.G. Turovets[12], B.A. Raizberg[13], L. Sh. V. Kutsenko[19], T.A. Govorushko[20], N.I. Klimash[21] and others conducted scientific research.

From local scientists on common problems of enterprises in Uzbekistan, issues of ensuring their competitiveness: M. Sharifkho'jayev[22], Yo.Abdullayev[23], N.K. Yoldoshev[24], R.I.Nurimbetov[25], Sh.N.Zaynutdinov[26]], S.K. Salayev[27], B.B. Jumaniyazov[28], K.S. Tashmukhamedova[29], U.I. Djumaniyazov[30], A. Abdullayev[31], Sh.A. Dekhkanov[32], A. Abdug'aniev[33] and others those who conducted scientific research.

In the works of the cited specialists, approaches to more enterprises and organizations, their impact on the general economy are widely and deeply studied, but the prospects for the formation of competitiveness of small business entities and the effective use and development of competitive advantages have not been described. This led to the selection of the research topic and determination of its goals and objectives.

Research methodology

Methods such as systematic analysis, statistical observation, statistical aggregation and grouping, selection, correlation and regression analysis, econometric modeling and forecasting were used in the research process.

Analysis and results

Construction, which occupies an important place in the country's economy, participates as an economic branch in the creation of basic funds for all sectors of the economy. Capital construction products mean production objects and non-production objects commissioned and accepted in the prescribed manner. The product defined as the end of the work done in the

construction becomes the fixed assets. Other sectors of the economy (construction materials industry, metallurgy, mechanical engineering and chemical industry, etc.) participate in their creation. Buildings and structures equipped with technological, energetic and other equipment and mechanisms make up the physical and material composition of the main production funds.

More than 70 sectors of the economy participate directly or indirectly in the field of capital construction, providing construction with metal and metal structures, cement, wood, construction machinery, vehicles, fuel and energy resources. In construction, 50% of the products of the building materials industry, about 18% of rolled metal, 40% of wood, and more than 10% of the products of the engineering industry are used. Construction is served by almost all branches of industry. Almost all types of transport such as road, rail, river, sea and air are used for transportation of construction materials, construction structures and construction equipment. The value of transportation costs in construction costs reaches 20%.

Thus, capital construction creates material conditions that enable the means of production to work. The construction industry combines the activities of general construction and specialized organizations, design-research and scientific-research organizations, construction industry enterprises in the framework of construction associations, as well as organizations that perform construction and assembly works economically. It can be seen that it is appropriate to express the efficiency of the construction industry through the synergistic effect of the mentioned industries.

The development of the national economy is determined by the dynamics of the gross domestic product formed in all its sectors. Construction, as an industry belonging to the material sphere, is designed to create and restore the main funds of all participants of the economic system - legal entities and individuals; budget and commercial organizations and others. The important role of construction requires careful provision of all necessary human, material, energy and information resources.

The development of construction, increasing its efficiency is carried out on the basis of its industrialization, as its main directions: transferring part of the technological processes from construction sites to factories, stationary production conditions in order to increase the volume of building assembly, and improving the technological design solutions of constructions, buildings and structures under construction, continuous construction work in order to ensure the production, it is possible to introduce a mechanized continuous process of technological operations and processes for the construction of buildings and structures, the supply of construction materials and structures.

In addition to the creation of fixed assets, capital construction functions include expansion, reconstruction and technical rearmament of existing fixed assets. That is why the main task of capital construction is the expanded reproduction and qualitative renewal of the main funds of all sectors of the country's economy.

Preparation for construction is carried out in the following areas: feasibility study of the technical and economic basis of construction of the object, design of the object and engineering-technical preparation for construction. Each direction has its own tasks. In the process of technical and economic studies, the main technical and economic indicators of the future facility are determined and the economic feasibility of its construction is assessed.

Thus, there is a need for optimal mutual development of related sectors and sub-sectors, which should include the building materials industry, without which the construction process is unthinkable. In this sense, at first, it was aimed to review the economic analysis of the activity of the construction industry in the Republic of Uzbekistan. (Table 1).

Table 1. Size and share of the construction industry in the gross domestic product of the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2010-2022 [34]

	Indicators	2010	2015	2020	2021	2022
1.	Gross domestic product, billion soums	78936,6	221350,9	605514,9	738425,2	888341,7
2.	Growth compared to last year, %	104,2	118,8	109,5	106,8	106,6
3.	Contribution of the construction industry to the gross domestic product, billion soums	8245,8	25423,1	88130,3	107492,7	123412,2
4.	Share of construction in GDP, %	5,4	5,7	6,7	6,6	6,7
5.	Investments in fixed capital, billion soums	16463,7	44810,4	210195,1	239552,6	251247,6
6.	Growth compared to last year, %	104,2	109,4	95,6	102,9	101,8
7.	Investments in construction, billion soums	9,9	40,1	228,1	142,8	287,0
8.	Growth compared to last year, %	99,1	100,3	100,1	101,4	100,6
9.	Volume of completed construction works, billion soums	25423,1	25423,1	88130,3	107492,7	112425,5
10.	Growth compared to last year, %	105,1	118,8	109,5	106,8	105,4

As can be seen from the table, all indicators of the volume of the construction industry in the gross domestic product of the Republic of Uzbekistan in the analyzed years 2010-2022 have an increasing trend, but although the indicator of completed construction works in 2020 increased by 0.3% compared to 2010, this indicator decreased compared to other periods. This, in turn, is explained by the fact that the work performed in the network in subsequent periods has passed from the quantity to the quality level.

As a result of the reforms in Uzbekistan in 2017-2022, the construction sector is growing faster than other sectors of the economy, in particular, agriculture - 1.2% in 2017, 0.3% in 2018, 3.1% in 2019, 3.0% in 2020, 4.0% in 2021, 3.6% in 2022 and production of industrial products 5.2% in 2017, 10.8% in 2018, 5.0% in 2019, 0.9% in 2020, 8% in 2021 .8%, and increased by 5.2% in 2022, while the construction volume in 2017-2022 is 6.0%, 14.3%, 22.9%, 9.5%, 6.8% and 6.6%, respectively. increased by %.

Also, the share of this sector in the structure of the national economy is increasing year by year. The share of the construction sector in the GDP was 6.6% in 2021, and in 2022 this indicator reached 6.7%. As of January 1, 2022, the number of enterprises and organizations in the construction sector is 41,000, which has increased by 1.7 times or 17,100 units compared to 2017.

Also, the number of people employed in construction will increase by 15,600 in 2022 compared to 2021, reaching 1.3 million. is forming a person. It should be said that about 10 percent of the people employed in the economy today belong to this sector. The volume of construction works completed in 2020 is 37.3 trillion. amounted to 45.6 trillion soums in 2021. soums and 55.5 trillion in 2022. amounted to soum. Also, when analyzing by types of economic activity, the main part of completed construction works corresponds to the volume of construction works of buildings and structures (74.5% share compared to the total indicator).

Another noteworthy point is that the share of the non-state sector in construction works is increasing, in 2020 this indicator was 95.2%, in 2021 it reached 95.8% and in 2022 it reached 96.1%. However, this is still not enough, because the share of construction in the composition of the gross domestic product remains largely unchanged. It is worth noting that the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On approval of the strategy of modernization, rapid and innovative development of the construction network of the Republic of Uzbekistan for 2021-

2025" [35] was of great importance in bringing the work in the construction sector to a new stage.

In the same way, if we pay attention to the results of the works carried out in the field of construction in the Namangan region, the decision "On the measures of wide introduction of information and communication technologies in the field of construction" [36] in order to increase the effectiveness of reforms on measures to ensure transparency in construction and fight against corruption, the decision of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On measures to fundamentally improve the quality of construction and assembly works and improve the construction control system"[37], aimed at implementing reforms to strengthen quality and control in construction, and the Cabinet of Ministers' "Administrative regulation on the implementation of state construction control in objects and Adoption of the decision on approval of classification of hazard categories of objects" [38] and ensuring its implementation in Namangan region led to positive results in the network (Table 2).

Table 2 Size and share of the construction industry in the gross regional product of Namangan region in 2010-2022

	Indicators	2010	2015	2020	2021	2022
1.	Gross regional product, billion soums	3364,4	10826,9	27863,0	34194,1	41098,2
2.	Growth compared to last year, %	110,3	107,7	105,1	109,7	106,6
3.	Contribution of the construction industry to the gross regional product, bln	197,3	452,4	2039,0	2410,2	2923,6
4.	The share of construction in the gross regional product, %	6,0	4,3	7,5	7,3	7,3
5.	Investments in fixed capital, billion soums	660,6	2227,5	12007,2	12982,0	14348,2
6.	Growth compared to last year, %	90,3	108,5	88,0	100,5	101,2
7.	Investments in construction, billion	9,9	40,1	228,1	142,8	287,0
8.	Growth compared to last year, %	99,1	100,3	100,1	101,4	100,6
9.	Volume of completed construction works, billion.	1010,4	4678,2	5556,7	6762,3	7132,3
10.	Growth compared to last year, %	132,9	102,6	118,3	109,1	110,3

If we pay attention to the average change of the gross regional product of Namangan province in 2010-2022, the average volume of the gross regional product is 16523.3 billion. changed to soums, and it should be noted that it increased by 7.4% on average over the years. During this period, the contribution of the construction industry to the gross regional product was equal to 5.7% on average. Such positive results achieved in the construction sector in Namangan region can be explained, first of all, as a result of the above-mentioned reforms, and secondly, with the increase in the volume of investments directed to the sector. That is, during the years 2010-2022, the average investment volume directed to the construction sector of Namangan region is 141.6 billion. amounted to 287.0 billion soums in 2022. is explained by the fact that it is equal to soum.

In recent years, the reforms in the country regarding the attraction of foreign investments, openness and transparency, the expansion of international cooperation and the creation of a favorable investment environment in the country have caused a sharp increase in the volume of foreign investments into fixed capital in the construction industry. In particular, this indicator is 12.1 million in 2017. 3.5 trillion soums in 2020. to the soum and 4.1 trillion in 2022 based on preliminary data. amounted to soum. The increase in capital investments directed to the construction sector serves to increase the creation of high-tech and technical production, modernization and construction of large infrastructures within the framework of investment and other programs.

Construction plays an important role in all sectors of the national economy, because it is due to construction that the infrastructure elements of the construction sector are created and improved (increased). Therefore, we can analyze the investment processes in various areas, including the construction capital of Namangan region in 2020-2022. (Table 3).

Table 3. Analysis of the volume of capital investments in the economy of the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2020-2022

Investment areas	Capital investments, in billion soums			Return on capital investments, %	
	2020	2021	2022	2022/2021	2022/2020
Total	12007	12982	13644	105,1	113,6
Agriculture, forestry and fisheries	1170,8	978,5	1028,4	105,1	87,8
Industry	4022	4542	4773,1	105,1	118,7
Construction	925,4	1838	1931,9	105,1	208,8
Wholesale and retail trade; repair of motor vehicles and motorcycles	1166,2	1015	1066,4	105,1	91,4
Transport, warehousing, postal and courier activities	785,3	614,3	645,6	105,1	82,2
Temporary accommodation and meals	94,1	86,2	90,6	105,1	96,3
Information and telecommunications	62,7	80,4	84,5	105,1	134,8

If we pay attention to the data presented in the table, you can see that the construction of the 7 main components of all investments listed in Table 3 has increased by 5.1 percent compared to 2020 and 208.8 percent compared to 2021. As you can see, their rapid increase is happening. In this regard, the amount of investment in information and telecommunications has been increased by 34.8 percent compared to 2021, especially in order to build "smart" buildings and facilities for the residents' living and efficient operation in the currently constructed facilities.

Figure 1. Correlation of total and investment capital investments of the construction industry

As can be seen from the figure, total capital investments grow faster than investments in construction, and capital investments in the construction sector amounted to 9.9 billion. 660.6 billion soums. It was 1.5 percent compared to the soum. It should also be noted that in 2022, compared to 2010, the volume of investments in construction has increased by almost 29.0 times. Over the past few years, there has been a positive trend in the overall construction performance as a result of the gradual transformation of the market. The volume of completed construction works by types of construction products in Uzbekistan during 2020-2022 is presented in Table 4 (Table 4).

As can be seen from the table, the total volume of construction in 2022 compared to 2013 will be 6762.3 billion. soums or increased by 25.1 percent. But in 2020, construction and almost all its structural elements (except for residential buildings), that is, a significant increase of 34.8% compared to 2019, was observed. In 2021, a slight stabilization of construction works is observed, but the total volume of construction from 2021 to 2020 is 5556.7 billion. increased to soums or 18.8 percent. Therefore, for the entire period, we see a growth rate higher than the chain rate in 2022.

Table 4 Volume of completed construction works in Namangan region by types of construction products

Year/increment	Construction, total	Building	From this		Engineering buildings
			Accommodation	Non-residential place	
2019, billion soums	3471	2547,7	2196,1	351,6	677,7
2020, billion soums	4678,2	3447,8	2954,8	493,0	906,8
Chain growth rate,%	134,8	135,3305	134,5	140,2	133,8
2021, billion soums	5556,7	4123,1	3430,4	692,7	1063,8
Chain growth rate,%	118,8	119,5844	116,1	140,5	117,3
2022, billion soums	6762,3	5125,8	4464,6	661,2	1240,4
Chain growth rate,%	121,7	124,3	130,1	95,5	116,6
Basic growth rates, %	125,1	126,4	126,9	125,4	122,6

It should be noted that in 2022, the total amount of construction work completed in the construction sector of Namangan region is 6762.3 billion. amounting to 4464.6 billion soums. soums, non-residential 661.2 billion soums. 1240.4 billion soums and engineering buildings. 1636.5 billion soums and other road construction, repair and reconstruction works. It is explained by the fact that the work of soums was completed and it was 25.1% higher than last year. Now let's look at the volume of construction works performed by the types of construction products presented in Table 5.

As can be seen from the table, buildings and engineering structures divide the structure of the total volume of construction by almost half, but since 2019, the volume of residential accommodation in the structure of buildings has been increasing. Over the entire period, the volume of residential buildings in the construction structure has a tendency to increase by 11.0 percent in 2022 compared to 2019.

Table 5. Composition of construction works by types of construction products, %

Years		2019 й	2020 й	2021 й	2022 й
Construction, total		100,0	100,0	100,0	100,0
Buildings		82,0	84,0	87,0	91,0
From this	Place of residence	72,0	76,0	83,0	85,0
	non-residential place	10,0	8,0	4,0	6,0
Engineering buildings		18,0	16,0	13,0	9,0

These residential buildings are the result of the urbanization taking place in our country and the formation of a modern and stable system of mortgage loans to individuals by our government in the provision of housing, targeted support by the state to families in need of improving housing conditions, financial support in local and international capital markets. In order to attract resources and then direct them to the refinancing of mortgage loans: "On measures to implement the program of providing housing to the population through mortgage loans based on market principles in 2023"[39], "Women's Notebook", "Youth Notebook" and in order to provide housing for women in need of housing included in the "Iron Book", to improve the living conditions of citizens who are homeless and in difficult living conditions in Tashkent, the Cabinet of Ministers "Provision of housing for women in need of housing and It was related to the implementation of decisions on measures to improve the living conditions of citizens who are homeless and in difficult living conditions in the city of Tashkent"[37].

These changes occur not only in the composition of the total volumes of construction, but also in the actual volumes of the types of construction products, for the analyzed period, there were only positive changes. In this sense, construction, like any other branch of the economy, serves to develop small business and private entrepreneurship in the region. The development of the construction industry inevitably leads to economic growth in the country and the solution of many social problems.

At the current stage, it is very difficult to talk about the competitiveness of this industry. If regionally, central districts and large millionaire cities have a tendency to dominate due to the large capacity and investment attractiveness of construction organizations, then at the global level, the construction industry of our country lags far behind due to the lack of necessary financial and organizational changes.

Of course, the development of the operation of the construction network is difficult to imagine without the successful development of relevant, existing supply networks. The construction process is characterized by a high level of material intensity, which, accordingly, leads the construction materials industry to a leading position in providing the necessary materials for the creation of construction products. The building materials industry is a multifaceted industry that includes more than twenty industries that make up a unique building materials market.

This means careful provision of human, material, energy and informational resources of construction. It should be noted that there is a need to develop industry, agriculture, transport and construction itself in optimal interrelationship with related industries, without which the construction process and the production of building materials cannot be imagined. This consideration also applies to the building materials market. It is very promising, so it is necessary to focus on it and conquer not only the domestic market, but also the foreign market.

Conclusions and suggestions

Research shows that it is proposed to develop a mechanism for ensuring cooperation with construction material production enterprises in coordinating the construction process with the strategic goals of socio-economic development of the region.

In short, capital construction creates material conditions that enable the means of production to work. The construction industry combines the activities of general construction and specialized organizations, design-research and scientific-research organizations, construction industry enterprises in the framework of construction associations, as well as organizations that perform construction and assembly works economically. It can be seen that it is appropriate to express the efficiency of the construction industry through the synergistic effect of the mentioned industries.

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